

Fusariosis symptomatology in fungal contamination of tomato fruits from the highlands of West Cameroon and effect of growing media and temperature on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp*

*Njimah Mfonmbouot D¹, Ndonkou Nfozon J², Lacmata Tamekou S², Tsopmbeng Noumbo GR¹ and Kuate JR²

¹Research Unit of Applied Botany, Faculty of Science, University of Dschang, Dschang, Cameroon

²Research Unit of Microbiology and Antimicrobial Substances, Faculty of Science, University of Dschang, Dschang, Cameroon

*Corresponding author: [Njimah Mfonmbouot Desiré](mailto:Njimah.Mfonmbouot@univ-dschang.cm)

Research Unit of Applied Botany, Faculty of Science, University of Dschang, Dschang, Cameroon

Tel: +237 699 19 86 14

Abstract

Fusariosis, major constraint on tomato production worldwide, causes enormous per-harvest and post-harvest losses. One of the causes of this loss is farmers lack of knowledge of the symptoms of this disease, making it difficult to identify and therefore to administer effective treatment. Thus, the aim of the present work was to describe the symptoms of fusariosis in fungal contamination of tomato fruits and to evaluate the influence of growing media and temperature on the growth of different morphotypes of Fusarium spp. isolated from tomato fruits from the highlands of West Cameroon. To achieve this objective, tomato growers were targeted in each production basin. From each grower, three crates of freshly packed fruit (in the field) were randomly selected. All fruit in each crate was carefully inspected for symptoms of fungal contamination. Fruits showing symptoms of fusariosis were set aside for the isolation of etiological agents. However, in the laboratory, fragments of the epicarp of these fruits were collected and cultured on Pomme de Terre Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium. Identification was made from the pure cultures obtained. After identification, the various Fusarium spp. were cultured on PDA, V8 and PPA media and then subjected to different temperatures in order to assess the influence of culture media and temperature respectively on their growth. Several fungal disease symptoms were observed on tomato fruits during the two years of the survey, but those of fusariosis were predominant and materialized by dull (orange-yellow) fruits with liquid lesions. The Fusarium oxysporium Fo₇ morphotype showed strong growth in all three growing media (between 08.20 and 06.90 cm). Overall, however, the PDA and V8 media favored the growth of the greatest number of Fusarium spp. morphotypes according to the Duncan test at $P \leq 0.05$. All F. oxysporium and F. solani morphotypes showed optimal radial growth at temperatures of 19 and 28°C, but no fungal growth was observed at 40°C. The results of this study provide valuable information for understanding the biology of Fusarium spp of tomato, which is essential for future effective control of this disease.

Keywords: Symptomatology, fusariosis, tomatoes, growing media, temperature, Fusarium spp.

1.Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.), annual herbaceous member of the Solanaceae family, is cultivated worldwide for its fruits, which contain large quantities of lycopene, a carotenoid with antioxidant properties (Liang *et al.*, 2021). According to some studies, lycopene may reduce the incidence of chronic diseases such as prostate, breast and cervical cancer (Giovannucci, 1999) and cardiovascular disorders (Freeman and Reimers, 2010). In addition to lycopene, tomatoes contain many other important health-promoting substances such as vitamin C, B vitamins, potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, iron, zinc, cobalt, nickel, fluoride and boron. It's a very popular vegetable all over the world, used to prepare various types of dishes such as stews, soups, salads and hamburgers. For its various properties and uses, global tomato production continues to rise, from over 130 million tonnes in 2014 to 182,301 million tonnes in 2018

(FAO, 2019), with China, India and the United States of America as the main producers. Cameroon's production is no exception, at 1,182,114 tonnes in 2019, with a yield of 12 kg per hectare, well below its production capacity (Atlas, 2021), which is thought to be linked to the problems faced by growers in the field (Njimah *et al.*, 2024). Added to this low productivity in the field are post-harvest losses. These losses are significant and can reach 40 to 90% (Benlamoudi *et al.*, 2019), causing shortages and inducing high prices (Ayinde *et al.*, 2014). These losses are due to biotic and abiotic constraints. Among biotic constraints, fungal diseases caused by species belonging to the genus *Fusarium* are the most important (Njimah *et al.*, 2021; Nikhat *et al.*, 2025). But in addition to their impact on post-harvest tomato losses in the various production basins in Cameroon, tomatoes contaminated by species of the *Fusarium* genus are dangerous to human health, as they produce mycotoxins (Heit, 2015). One of the reasons for the rapid development of this disease is that farmers are unaware of its symptoms, which they say are similar to those of other fungal diseases. In addition to this biotic constraint, there are abiotic constraints such as climatic factors. This could provide valuable information for understanding the biology of *Fusarium*, with a view to effective control of the disease in the future. The work of Dossa *et al.*, 2019 has shown that the severity of diseases caused by *Fusarium* fungi of oil palms depends on environmental and climatic factors. Similarly, Bernard, 2012 showed that temperature influences the development of species belonging to the genus *Fusarium* isolated from palms, and is generally an essential parameter in the development of phytopathogenic fungi of date palms. While there have been previous studies on the factors influencing the growth of *Fusarium spp.* on palms, there is little or no information on the criteria for differentiating symptoms of fusariosis on tomatoes, let alone on the temperatures and nutrient environments affecting the growth and development of the fungal species associated with this disease in the West Cameroon region. The availability of such information is a necessary basis for developing an effective control strategy against this disease. It is in this context that the aim of the present work was to describe the symptoms of fusariosis in the fungal contamination of tomato fruit, and to evaluate the influence of growing media and temperature on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.* isolated from tomato fruit from the highlands of West Cameroon.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Description of symptoms of fusariosis in fungal contamination of tomato fruits

Symptoms of some fungal diseases observed on tomato fruit were described, and their prevalence assessed, using fruit collected from gardeners in the various production basins of Dschang (Zimsop, Kemsop and FASA experimental site), Fombot (Baigom, Fchieya and Fosset) and Mbouda (Babete, Balachi and Bamenkombo). For this purpose, three crates of fruit were randomly selected from each collection site for each field trip thus nine crates for each basin for the three field trips. Each crate contained around 350 fruits, for a total of 3,150 fruits per production basin. Each fruit was meticulously examined for symptoms of fungal diseases, particularly fusariosis (Njimah *et al.*, 2021).

2.2. Evaluation of the influence of culture media on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.*

2.2.1. Isolation of different *Fusarium spp.*

Tomato fruits showing symptoms of fusariosis were transported to the Phytopathology and Agricultural Zoology Research Unit, where they were first washed separately with tap water, then superficially disinfected using cotton soaked in 70° alcohol (Wamalwa *et al.*, 2018). Epidermal fragments measuring around 2 mm² were removed under a microbiological hood near the flame of a Bunsen burner using a sterile scalpel. These fragments were then disinfected in a 5% sodium hypochlorite solution for 5 minutes, then rinsed 3 times in succession with distilled water to remove traces of disinfectant, before being placed on sterilized paper to remove excess water. These fragments were aseptically seeded into 90 mm glass Petri dishes containing 20 ml of PDA medium at a rate of 5 fragments per Petri dish, and placed in the dark in an incubator at laboratory room temperature (24 ± 2°C). Observations were made daily on each Petri dish, looking for the beginnings of fungal growth (colony) around the fragment deposited on the culture medium. When fungal growth was observed around the inoculated fragments, subculturing was immediately carried out in new Petri dishes containing PDA medium. After several successive transplants, pure cultures of the various fungal isolates were obtained and identified under the microscope. The different pure cultures of each *Fusarium* morphotype were kept for further study (Njimah *et al.*, 2024).

2.2.2. Influence of culture media on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.*

Three culture media, namely PDA (Potato Agar); V8 (culture media consisting of eight ingredients); PPA (Papaya Agar) were used to evaluate the influence of culture media on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.* A 0.5 cm diameter mycelial explant was taken from the growth front of each 10-day-old pure mycelial culture and aseptically placed in the center of a Petri dish containing 20 ml of each culture medium. Three plates were seeded for each morphotype. Incubation took place in the dark at 24 ± 2°C for 10 days. The radial growth of the fungus in each Petri dish was measured each day along two perpendicular directions traced on the reverse side of the Petri dish and passing through the center of the mycelial deposit. The radial growth diameter of the colony was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Radial growth (cm)} = \frac{d1 + d2}{2} - d0$$

Where: d1 and d2 = diameter of radial growth in both directions, d0 = diameter of die.

2.3. Evaluation of the influence of temperature on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.*

Pure 10-day-old cultures of the various morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.* were subcultured in PDA culture media as described above. The various Petri dishes were incubated at different temperatures notably 19, 28 and 40°C for 10 days. Data were collected on the radial growth diameter and calculated according to the formula presented above (Njimah, 2022).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Fusariosis symptoms in fungal contamination of tomato fruit

In the three production basins selected (Dschang, Foubot and Mbouda), symptoms of fungal diseases observed on tomato fruit during the two years of the survey included black, sunken lesions at the point of attachment, damp, circular black spots on red fruit, gray fruits with spectral spots in the form of halos, sometimes with a small black dot in the center; dull (orange-yellow) fruits with liquid lesions; mottled brown lesions, sometimes with a copper bump and whitish down, characteristic of alternariosis (Figure B), anthracnose, botrytis or gray rot (Figure A), fusariosis (Figure C) and mildew (Figure D) respectively. All these diseases and their symptoms are summarized in Table 1. The various fungal diseases observed during this work are similar to those reported by Abdeselem (2017) and Asma *et al.* (2018) on tomatoes. These diseases have been numerous and diverse. The diversity of these diseases may be due to the extreme variability of fungal species associated with tomato fruits. These results are similar to those of Sajad *et al.* (2017) who reported in their work on the inventory of fungi associated with post-harvest rots of tomato fruits in the different markets of Jabalpur and Madhya-Pradesh in India that fungal diseases associated with tomato fruits are numerous and vary both according to the species involved and its degree of aggressiveness.

Figure : Some fungal diseases observed on tomato fruits, (A): Botrytis or grey rot; (B): Alternariose (C): Fusariosis and (D): Mildew

Table 1 : Fungal diseases observed on tomato fruits in Dschang, Foubot and Mbouda in 2017 and 2018.

Production areas	Symptoms	Diseases
Dschang	Damp circular black spots on red fruit	Anthracoise
	Marbled brown lesions, sometimes with coppery bumps and whitish down	Mildew
	Orange-yellow fruit with liquid lesions	Fusariosis
	Deep black lesions at point of attachment	Alternarioise
	Gray fruit with halo-shaped spots, sometimes with a small black dot in the center.	Botrytis
Foubot	Damp circular black spots on red fruit	Anthracoise
	Marbled brown lesions, sometimes with coppery bumps and whitish down	Mildew
	Orange-yellow fruit with liquid lesions	Fusariosis
	Deep black spot at attachment point	Alternarioise
	Fruits gray in color with halo-shaped spots, sometimes with a small black dot in the center.	Botrytis
Mbouda	Damp circular black spots on red fruit	Anthracoise
	Marbled brown lesions, sometimes with coppery bumps and whitish down	Mildew
	Orange-yellow fruit with liquid lesions	Fusariosis
	Deep black spot at attachment point	Alternarioise
	Fruits gray in color with halo-shaped spots, sometimes with a small black dot in the center	Botrytis

3.2. Influence of culture media on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.*

Table 2 shows the effect of culture media on the radial growth of the different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.* From this table it can be seen that the growth of each morphotype varied according to the culture medium. Overall, however, the PDA and V8 media were the ones that favored the growth of the greatest number of *Fusarium spp.* morphotypes, according to the Ducan test at $P \leq 0.05$. This would mean that the various nutrients in the composition of these two culture media (PDA and V8) are those most consumed by species belonging to the genus *Fusarium* to ensure their growth. Similar results were obtained by Sédra, 1993, who also showed that PDA culture media were favorable for the growth of *Fusarium oxysporium* responsible for vascular fusariosis of palms, and that V8 media were the best media for the production of spores of fungi belonging to the *Fusarium* genus. Similarly, those of Sushila *et al* (2022) showed that the PDA culture medium was the most favorable for the growth of *Fusarium oxysporium*, with an average growth of 88.04 mm, followed by the oatmeal-based agar medium. Furthermore, the *Fusarium oxysporium* Fo₇ morphotype showed strong growth in all three culture media, suggesting that this morphotype is a ubiquitous fungus that grows in all media and has no preferred culture medium.

Table 2: Effect of culture media on radial growth (cm/d) of *Fusarium spp.*

<i>Fusarium</i> species	Morphotypes	Culture media		
		PDA	V8	PPA
Year 2017				
<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>	Fo ₁	07.75±00.25 ^{bc*}	05.73±00.06 ^d	05.07±00.90 ^{cd}
	Fo ₂	08.20±00.00 ^a	04.77±00.06 ^e	04.63±00.32 ^d
	Fo ₃	07.68±00,16 ^c	06.60±00.10 ^e	05.00±00.00 ^d
	Fo ₄	07.90±00.14 ^b	06.80±00.35 ^{bc}	05.93±00.40 ^{bc}
	Fo ₅	08.20±00.00 ^a	05.17±00.29 ^e	04.93±00.06 ^d
	Fo ₆	07.37±00,15 ^d	06.67±00.58 ^{bc}	05.53±00.50 ^{bcd}
	Fo ₇	08.20±00.00 ^a	08.10±00.17 ^a	07.37±00.06 ^a
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	Fs ₁	08.20±00.00 ^a	07.13±00.23 ^b	06.27±00.32 ^b
	Fs ₂	08.19±00.01 ^a	06.97±00.06 ^{bc}	05.93±00.81 ^{bc}
Year 2018				

<i>F.oxysporum</i>	F01	08,03±00,06 ^a	05,13±00,58 ^c	04,37±00,55 ^b
	F02	08,15±00,05 ^a	04,07±00,64 ^d	03,93±00,81 ^b
	F03	07,76±00,06 ^b	06,30±00,44 ^b	04,37±00,06 ^b
	F04	08,03±00,06 ^a	07,60±00,53 ^a	04,77±00,60 ^b
	F05	08,08±00,08 ^a	04,83±00,76 ^{cd}	04,00±00,87 ^b
	F06	07,73±00,29 ^b	07,20±00,00 ^a	04,86±00,64 ^b
	F07	08,15±00,05 ^a	07,93±00,06 ^a	06,90±00,00 ^a
<i>F.solani</i>	Fs1	08,13±00,06 ^a	07,45±00,53 ^a	05,17±01,15 ^b
	Fs2	08,11±00,12 ^a	07,40±00,56 ^a	04,90±00,78 ^b

* Means with the same superscript letter in the same column are not significantly different according to the Duncan multiple test at $P \leq 0.05$.

3.3. Influence of temperature on the growth of different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.*

The table opposite shows the effect of temperature on radial growth (cm/d) of *Fusarium spp.* It can be seen from this table that the most favorable temperatures for growth of the different morphotypes of *Fusarium solani* and *F. oxysporum* are those between 19 and 28°C, whereas at 40°C almost no fungal growth was observed at $P \leq 0.05$ (Table 3). This could be due to the fact that each *Fusarium* species has a temperature optimum at which disease expression is maximal. These results are similar to those of Rossi et al., 2001, who demonstrated in their work that *F. graminearum* and *F. avenaceum* have their optimum at 28-29°C, while *F. culmorum* has its optimum at 26.5°C. According to Bernard (2012), temperature influences the development of species belonging to the *Fusarium* genus, and is generally an essential parameter in the development of phytopathogenic fungi. It strongly influences most metabolic processes in living organisms, and affects almost every aspect of their growth and development. Indeed, the work of Doohan et al. (2003) demonstrated that it has a strong influence on spore production in *Fusarium spp.* However, morphotypes of the same species from different origins may have different optimum growth temperatures in relation to the climate prevailing in their locality of origin.

Table 3: Effect of temperature on radial growth (cm/day) of *Fusarium spp.*

<i>Fusarium</i> species	Morphotypes	Temperatures		
		19 °C	28 ° C	40 °C
		Year 2017		
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	F01	05.01±00.59 ^{c*}	06.92±00.03 ^c	00.00±00.00 ^c
	F02	05.96±00.02 ^b	08.20±00.00 ^a	00.00±00.00 ^c
	F03	04.95±00.69 ^c	06.33±00.14 ^d	00.00±00.00 ^c
	F04	05.75±00.01 ^b	07.76±00.01 ^b	00.00±00.00 ^c
	F05	05.42±00.14 ^{bc}	07.58±00.58 ^b	00.00±00.00 ^c
	F06	07.13±00.23 ^a	08.18±00.02 ^a	00.00±00.00 ^c
	F07	07.10±00.17 ^a	07.80±00.61 ^b	00.80±00.26 ^b
<i>Fusarium solani</i>	Fs1	07.05±00.12 ^a	08.18±00.00 ^a	00.00±00.00 ^c
	Fs2	07.03±00.06 ^a	08.20±00.00 ^a	01.47±00.12 ^a
		Year 2018		
<i>F.oxysporum</i>	F01	03,70±00,87 ^d	07,30±00,35 ^b	00,00±00,00 ^b
	F02	04,48±00,04 ^b	08,17±00,05 ^a	00,00±00,00 ^b
	F03	03,83±00,14 ^{cd}	07,32±00,28 ^b	00,00±00,00 ^b
	F04	04,40±00,26 ^b	08,03±00,12 ^a	00,00±00,00 ^b
	F05	04,27±00,06 ^{bc}	08,18±00,03 ^a	00,00±00,00 ^b

	Fo6	06,87±00,12 ^a	08,20±00,01 ^a	00,00±00,00 ^b
	Fo7	06,94±00,05 ^a	07,88±00,39 ^a	00,17±00,01 ^{ab}
<i>F.solani</i>	Fs1	06,97±00,06 ^a	08,13±00,06 ^a	00,00±00,00 ^b
	Fs2	06,70±00,10 ^a	08,13±00,12 ^a	00,30±00,10 ^a

* Means with the same superscript letter in the same column are not significantly different according to the Duncan multiple test at $P \leq 0.05$.

4. Conclusion

With a view to combating Fusariosis in tomatoes, the symptoms of this disease were described to facilitate its identification by farmers, and the influence of growing media and temperature were assessed on the growth of the different morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.* isolated from these tomato fruits from the highlands of West Cameroon. The results of this study showed that the symptoms of fungal diseases observed on tomato fruits were numerous, but those of fusariosis were preponderant and materialized by dull (orange-yellow) fruits with liquid lesions. These results also showed that temperatures of 19 and 28°C and nutrient media PDA and V8 favor the growth of fungal species associated with this disease. The availability of this information is a necessary basis for developing an effective control strategy against this disease. However, it would be advisable to continue this study by investigating the effect of culture media and temperature, as well as other environmental factors, on sporulation of these morphotypes of *Fusarium spp.*

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest

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